

Report of the Independent International Commission on Decommissioning (IICD), 22 March 2001

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To: The Rt Hon. John Reid, MP Secretary of State for Northern Ireland, Belfast	To: Mr. John O'Donoghue, TD, Minister of Justice, Equality and Law Reform, Dublin
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1. Since our 22 December 2000 report to the Governments there has been no actual decommissioning, but events of the past few weeks lead us to believe that progress on it can be made. This report will comment on those events.
2. Meetings in recent weeks with representatives of the UVF and the UFF confirmed their willingness to consider decommissioning their arms, and their general agreement on methods and related supporting issues. Both groups continue to affirm that they will not move on decommissioning before the IRA does so.
3. On 8 March the IRA published a statement in which they stated in part: "...the IRA leadership has decided to enter into further discussions with the IICD. This will be on the basis of the IRA leadership's commitment to resolving the issues contained in our statement of May 6th 2000, and on no other basis." In a telephone call later the same day, the IRA renewed contact with the Commission.
4. Subsequently a meeting was held between the Commission and the IRA representative. At that meeting we reviewed developments since our last meeting and established a basis for further discussions. We welcomed the re-engagement with the IRA representative and consider it to be in good faith. We will build on it at future such meetings which we expect will occur soon.
5. We will keep the Governments advised of progress as it occurs.

Signed: Tauno Nieminen John de Chastelain Andrew D. Sens

Belfast, 22 March 2001

Dublin Office Dublin Castle Block M, Ship Street DUBLIN 2 Tel No: 00 353 (0)1 4780111 Fax No: 00 353 (0)1 4780600	Belfast Office Rosepark House Upper Newtownards Road BELFAST BT4 3NX Tel No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8600 Fax No: 00 44 (0)28 9048 8601
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